

Working Capital Management and Corporate Profitability of Japanese Firms

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between working capital management, profitability, firm size and industry for firms in Japan. The analysis is based on a sample of 2123 Japanese non-financial firms listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange for the period 1990-2004. We observe that the cash conversion cycle and return on investment relationships are commonly significant and negative. Overall, the findings indicate that shortening the cash conversion cycle enhances the profitability of Japanese firms.

Keywords: Working Capital Management; Cash Conversion Cycle; Receivable Collection Period; Inventory Conversion Period; Payable Deferral Period; Return On Investment

JEL classification: G30; G39

1. Introduction

Maximization of the owner's wealth is the basic financial goal in the management of corporations. To achieve this goal management should focus on both long term and short term financial management decisions. Although the traditional focus in corporate finance was on long-term financial decisions, particularly on capital structure, dividends, investments, and company valuation decisions, the recent trend in corporate finance is a focus on working capital management (Ganesan, 2007). Working capital management contributes to the realization of this goal, especially in a tough economy; an organization with a proper set of working capital management practices will improve profitability, reduce the risk of corporate failure and significantly improve its chances of survival. It also provides a strategic advantage, especially in difficult economic times (Jose et al., 1996).

Working capital management is about managing current assets and current liabilities. It is an essential component of corporate finance since it affects the firm's liquidity, profitability, cash flow and market value (Alshattarat et al., Deloof, 2003; Mathuva, 2010; Nobanee et al.; 2011; Raheman and Nasr, 2007). Firms with inadequate cash and inventory levels may incur shortages that could disturb the firm's operations (Appuhami, 2008). Among comprehensive performance measures for assessing how well a company is managing its current assets and current liabilities is the cash conversion cycle suggested by Richards and Laughlin (1980). Stewart (1995) defines the cash conversion cycle as "a composite metric describing the average days required to turn a dollar invested in raw materials into a dollar collected from a customer". Besley and Brigham (2005) describes the cash conversion cycle as " the length of time from the payment for

the purchase of raw materials to manufacturing a product until the collection of account receivable associated with the sale of the product” (Nobanee, et al, 2011). The short cash conversion cycle indicates that the firm is collecting the receivables as quickly as possible and delaying the payments to suppliers as slowly as possible. This results to high firm’s value, profitability, cash flow and liquidity (Alshattarat et al., Deloof, 2003; Gentry et al., 1990; Mathuva, 2010; Nobanee et al., 2011; Raheman and Nasr, 2007; Nobanee and AlHajjar, 2014).

A great deal of research in the area of the efficiency of working capital management and its effect on the firm’s profitability, liquidity, cash flow and market value was carried out worldwide (Afza and Nazir, 2007; Alshattarat et al., 2010; Chowdhury and Amin, 2007; Christopher and Kamalavalli, 2009; Deloof, 2003; Ganesan, 2007; Lazaridis and Tryfonidis, 2006; Mathuva, 2010; Mohamad and Saad, 2010; Narware, 2004; Nobanee et al., 2011; Padachi,2006; Raheman and Nasr, 2007; Sayaduzzaman, 2006; Shin and Soenen; 1998; Uyar, 2009). However, the impact of different working capital management practices on the profitability Japanese firms might be imprecisely different from that of firms in other countries due to the unique Japanese company structure and business environment. This paper aims at contributing to the knowledge of the cash conversion cycle and its relation to the firm’s performance in Japan. As the Japanese business environment is relatively different from that of other top economies of the world, it is interesting to examine whether the characteristics of the Japanese firm might have an effect on their cash conversion cycle and, therefore, their profitability.

The rest of the paper is organized along the following lines. Section two presents the data and the methodology used. Section three documents the analysis and the results. Finally, section four concludes the paper.

2. Data and Methodology

The data set in this study was retrieved from *DataStream*. The data includes all the non-financial firms listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange. Some firms with missing data are excluded from the sample. The final sample contains 2123 companies covering the period between 1990 and 2004.

Return on investment is used as a profitability measure. It is defined as net income divided by total capital invested. The receivable collection period measures the time lag between the sale of goods and the collection of cash. It is measured as $[(\text{account receivable}/\text{sales}) * 365]$. The inventory conversion period is the time lag between the payments of cash for raw materials and the sale of finished goods. It is measured as $[(\text{inventory}/\text{cost of goods sold}) * 365]$. The payable deferral period is the time lag between the purchase of goods and the payments made for them. It is calculated as $[(\text{account payable}/\text{cost of goods sold}) * 365]$. The cash conversion cycle is an additive function calculated as $[\text{Receivable collection period} + \text{Inventory conversion period} - \text{Payable deferral period}]$ (Nobanee et al, 2011).

To test the effect of the cash conversion cycle and its components on profitability, we apply a robust regression which is usually used in cases of subsection of heteroskedasticity, the presence of outliers and when the errors distribution is not normal. We regress the cash conversion cycle, the receivable collection period, the inventory

conversion period and the payable deferral period against the return on investment for the full study sample and for different size levels and industries.

3. Empirical Results

Table 1 below reports the results of the robust linear regression of the relationship between the working capital management and the firm's performance for a sample of 2318 Japanese non-financial firms listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange, for the period 1990-2004. The dependent variable is the return on investment (ROI) and the independent variables include the receivables collection period (RCP), the inventory conversion period (ICP), the payable deferral period (PDP), and the cash conversion cycle (CCC). Table 1 reports the results of the full sample besides the divisions of the sample by size levels and industries. The results show that the coefficients of the receivable collection period for all companies, small companies, and service companies are negative and significant. This indicates that reducing the receivable collection period increases the profitability of such companies. The results also show that the inventory conversion period is significantly and negatively related to profitability for all companies, small companies, medium companies, general industries, service companies, and information technology companies. The negative and significant relation of the inventory conversion period is consistent with the view that companies with low inventory levels reduce the holding inventory cost that leads to high profitability. The results of the relation between payable deferral period and profitability show significant and positive relationship for service companies. This positive and significant relationship between

payable deferral period and profitability for service companies indicates that delaying payments to suppliers saves some cash that could be reinvested in the company's operations which leads to increases in the firm's profitability. The results also show a significant and negative relationship between the cash conversion cycle and the firm's profitability for all companies, medium companies, and service companies. This negative and significant relationship can be explained by that fact that reducing the average period of time between the payment for inventory and the collection of cash from receivables increases the firm's profitability.

Table 1
Robust Regression Results of the Relationship between the Working Capital Management and Firm's Performance

Sample	Coefficients				
	RCP	ICP	PDP	CCC	Constant
All Companies	-.021349**	-8.76e-07***	-.0022658	-.0065667*	6.807095***
Small Companies	-.0379159*	-1.36e-06***	-.0160005	-.0034826	9.931924***
Medium Companies	.0002834	-3.04e-07***	-.0091171	-.0136166**	5.834084***
Large Companies	.0205498	.0225022	-.0186875	-.0314522	4.166654***
Basic Industries	-.0196376	-.017453	.0123574	.0103521	4.410255***
General Industries	-.005592	-6.70e-07**	-.018283	-.0053523	6.177269
Consumer Goods	-.0382888	-.0213756	.0130615	.0265092	5.608664***
Service Companies	-.2318365*	-.2160266*	.2242896*	.2097595*	5.524961***
Information Technology	-.050666	-.1229236***	.0616149	.0510896	11.66494***

Table 1 reports the results of a robust linear regression for the relationship between working capital management and firm's performance for a sample of 2318 Japanese non-financial firms listed in the Tokyo Stock Exchange, for the period 1990-2004. The dependent variable is the return on investment (ROI) and the independent variables includes; (RCP) the receivables collection period, (ICP) the inventory conversion period, (PDP) the payable deferral period, and (CCC) the cash conversion cycle. Table 1 reports the results of the full sample and divisions of the sample by size and industry.

Note: * significant at 90% confidence level, ** significant at 95% confidence level, *** significant at 99% confidence level

4. Conclusion

The cash conversion cycle is one of the comprehensive measures of the efficiency of working capital management. The existing literature studied worldwide in the area of the efficiency of working capital management suggests that the short cash conversion cycle is associated with a high firm's profitability (Afza and Nazir, 2007; Alshattarat et al., 2010;

Chowdhury and Amin, 2007; Christopher and Kamalavalli, 2009; Deloof, 2003; Ganesan, 2007; Lazaridis and Tryfonidis, 2006; Mathuva, 2010; Mohamad and Saad, 2010; Narware, 2004; Nobanee et al.; 2011; Padachi,2006; Raheman and Nasr, 2007; Sayaduzzaman, 2006; Shin and Soenen; 1998; Uyar, 2009) Our findings in this paper are in line with these results. In this study we examined the effect of working capital management practices on the firm's profitability from the Japanese perspective that could be imprecisely different than other countries due to the unique Japanese company structure and business environment. Our results show that slow collections of account receivables boosts the firm's profitability, while reducing inventory levels improves its profitability. The results also show that reducing the time lag between the payments for inventory and the collection cash from receivables results in a higher firm's profitability. The findings of our paper indicate that Japanese firms can increase their profitability by shortening the cash conversion cycle, shortening the receivable collection period and shorting the inventory conversion periods.

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